

APRIORI ALGORITHM TO ANALYSE STUDENTS PERFORMANCE

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Abstract— Predicting academic accomplishment is a critical goal in the field of education as it can reveal the elements that determine the degree to which a student performs and recommend activities that enhance learning outcomes. In this research, we offer a method for analyzing student performance that makes use of association rule mining and the Apriori algorithm. We develop frequent item sets and association rules that can be used to spot patterns and interactions between various parameters using information from a dataset of student performance, including grade point averages, comments, and language preferences. In order to group students according to their performance in the data set, we additionally use performance level categories. We then employ our strategy to rank the best 5, worst, and average pupils using association rules. Our findings demonstrate that this method is useful for spotting trends and connections between various variables and can be applied to forecast student performance. We come to the conclusion that interventions aiming at enhancing student performance and learning outcomes may be informed by our methodology.

Keywords- Association rule, Apriori algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

A significant area of educational study is the performance analysis of students. Analyzing student performance can assist educators and researchers in better understanding the elements that influence a student's success or failure and informing interventions meant to enhance learning outcomes. Data mining and machine learning approaches are becoming increasingly popular for analyzing student performance data as educational data becomes more widely available. In this research, we offer a method for assessing student performance that makes use of association rule mining and the Apriori algorithm.

In this paper, we propose a method for evaluating student performance using association rule mining and the Apriori algorithm. Our approach is supported by data on student performance, including typical grades, feedback, and preferred languages. We use the Apriori method to rate frequent item sets and association rules that can be used to discover patterns and connections between different parameters.

The dataset used in our analysis includes data on 120 students, including their average grades, feedback, and

preferred languages. The feedback column contains categorical variables such as "poor performance," "needs improvement," "good performance," and "excellent," which describe the students' performance feedback. Java, Python, PHP, & React are the programming languages indicated as students' top choices in the language column.

In order to study the dataset, we first converted the feedback and language columns into categorical variables using the Pandas library's `pd.Categorical` function. Then, using the `pd.cut` function, we assigned students to one of four performance levels—poor, average, good, or excellent—based on their average marks for the course. The data was then converted into a one-hot encoded format using the `pd.get_dummies` function, which may be used to create frequent item collections and association rules.

We generated frequent item set and association rules with a minimum support of 0.2 using the Apriori technique. The Apriori algorithm is a popular technique for producing frequent item sets and association rules, and it works especially well with huge and intricate datasets. The technique operates by iteratively creating candidate item sets and removing any that do not satisfy a minimal support level. We determined best, worst, and average-performing students for each performance level using the association rules produced by the Apriori algorithm.

Compared to conventional statistical methods for assessing student performance, our approach provides a number of benefits. First, it can spot intricate patterns and connections between several aspects that are challenging to spot with conventional techniques. Additionally, it can manage complicated and huge datasets, which are increasingly popular in education research. Last but not least, it can offer practical insights that can guide actions aimed at raising student achievement and learning outcomes.

II. ASSOCIATION RULE MINING

In order to study patterns and interactions among many variables in education research, association rule mining is a potent data mining tool. In this work, we used association rule mining to examine student performance data and pinpoint the variables most closely linked to academic success.

The Apriori algorithm, a popular association rule mining tool, is used to discover frequent itemset and association rules in huge datasets. We used this method to analyze student performance data in our study to identify correlations between a number of variables, such as feedback, grades, and programming language choices.

Data transformation into a one-hot encoded format is the initial stage in association rule mining. The Apriori algorithm needs each variable to be represented as a binary value, so this is done to make sure it is. The Apriori method is then used to create frequent item sets. These are examples of frequent variable combinations found in the dataset.

The final step is to create association rules using the frequent item sets. Association rules are logical assertions that explain the connections between various variables. An association rule might, for instance, declare that "students who receive positive feedback and prefer Python are more likely to achieve high marks." The strength and significance of the links between various variables are measured by a number of assessment metrics, including lift and confidence, which are used to produce these rules.

The analysis of the findings to determine the variables most strongly linked to academic success is the last step in the association rule mining process. Using this data, plans can be created to raise academic standards and student performance.

As a result, association rule mining is a useful technique for identifying patterns and linkages in huge datasets. This technique can be used to analyze information about student performance in order to find the elements most closely related with academic success and generate strategies for increasing student performance.

III. APRIORI ALGORITHM

The Apriori algorithm is a popular algorithm for association rule mining. It works by detecting common itemset in a dataset and producing association rules from those itemset. In the context of student performance analysis, the Apriori algorithm can be used to find patterns and links among various academic measures such as test scores, grades, attendance, and involvement.

The first step in implementing the Apriori algorithm is to transform the dataset to binary format, where every statistic can be represented as a binary variable (1 if the metric exceeds a specified threshold, 0 otherwise). This is referred to as one-shot encoding. The one-shot encoded dataset is then put into the Apriori algorithm.

The Apriori algorithm generates potential itemset of increasing size iteratively and prunes those itemset that do not match a minimal support criteria (i.e., the percentage of transactions including the itemset). The remaining frequent itemset are then used to produce association rules, which are

rules of the type "if A then B", where A and B are sets of items.

In the context of educational achievement analysis, the Apriori algorithm can be used to build association rules that show interesting patterns and relationships among various academic indicators. For example, it may disclose that students who perform well on a certain test also have satisfactory attendance rates, or that students who contribute more in class have higher marks.

Overall, the Apriori method is a great tool for detecting significant connections and patterns in student performance data. Educators and academics can get significant insights into the aspects that contribute to academic achievement by creating association rules and visualizing them in a directed graph.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Saini and Goyal (2020) [1], utilized the Apriori algorithm to analyze student performance data and discover the elements that impact student success. They collected data on numerous student qualities such as attendance, class involvement, and exam results and utilized the Apriori method to discover common itemset and association rules among these traits.

The researchers discovered that attendance and class involvement were the most important variables impacting student success after analyzing the information using the Apriori algorithm. They also discovered that students who scored well on tests had higher levels of attendance and involvement in class. This implies that attending courses and engaging in class activities are critical components of academic achievement.

The results of the research have ramifications for teachers and administrators since they emphasize the importance of class engagement and attendance in student performance. Instructors may be able to enhance student outcomes and assist more kids achieve academic achievement by concentrating on these aspects. Their observation illustrates the Apriori algorithm's effectiveness in analyzing educational data and identifying factors affecting academic success. It also emphasizes the relevance of class participation and attendance in student success, which has significant consequences for educational policy and practice.

Alizadeh et al. (2020) [2], employed the Apriori algorithm to assess the high school students academic performance. The study discovered that kids who engaged in various kinds of extracurricular activities scored better academically.

The study discovered that students who participated in extracurricular activities performed better than those who did not. The study also discovered that kids who were more involved in extracurricular activities had better attendance and were more likely to be admitted into college. Overall, the study's findings indicate that participation in extracurricular activities can improve high school students' academic

performance. The study provides insights for teachers and authorities who want to design measures to encourage and support student participation in extracurricular activities.

Gouda and Hassanien (2020) [3], developed an association rule mining-based technique for predicting student success in e-learning systems. The authors gathered information on numerous student qualities such as course completion rate, quiz scores, forum engagement, and video views. They employed the Apriori technique to extract common items and association rules between these qualities.

Their findings demonstrated that the suggested method was effective in predicting student performance in e-learning systems. They discovered that forum involvement, quiz scores, and video views were the most significant factors impacting student achievement.

The work of Hameed et al. (2021) [4], study the use of association rule mining in analysing student performance data in a university context. The Apriori technique is used in the study to extract frequent itemset and association rules from a dataset that contains information on student grades, course attendance, and online participation.

The findings indicate that the Apriori algorithm was capable of extracting meaningful association rules that were important to student performance. The authors discovered that students who attended class regularly and engaged in online conversations performed better academically. Also, the study discovered that students with lower grades had lower levels of interaction with the online course platform.

Arora and Mittal (2022)[5], suggested a strategy based on association rule mining to predict students' academic success. They gathered information on numerous student qualities such as attendance, exam results, and class involvement and utilized the Apriori technique to identify common itemset and association rules between these attributes. Attendance, past academic achievement, and gender were found to be major determinants impacting students' academic success. They also discovered that male students beat female students academically.

V. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

We implemented a system that returns the performance of the student as excellent, good, average etc.. The read_csv function is used to import the student performance dataset into a pandas dataframe as the first step in the technique. The information includes features such as average grades, project language, and comments. Fig1 shows the code to read dataset. Dataset includes studentid, average mark, feedback, language used for the project and name of the students. Fig2 shows the dataset for the evaluation purpose By executing read_csv output is as Fig 3. Python implementation of the Apriori algorithm using the mlxtend package

Fig1

```

1 import pandas as pd
2 from mlxtend.frequent_patterns import apriori, association_rules
3
4 # Load the student performance dataset
5 df = pd.read_csv('student_performance_data.csv')
6 df
7

```

Fig2

STUDENT	avg_mark	feedback	language	name
S001	90	good perf	python	anu
S002	70	need impr	react	appu
S003	95	excellent	java	manu
S004	60	poor perf	php	manav
S005	55	poor perf	java	balu
S006	73	need impr	java	binu
S007	75	need impr	python	cini
S008	70	need impr	python	diya
S009	98	excellent	java	asha
S010	96	excellent	python	amina
S011	74	need impr	php	ammu

Fig 3

	STUDENT ID	avg_mark	feedback	language	name
0	S001	90	good performance	python	anu
1	S002	70	need improvement	react	appu
2	S003	95	excellent	java	manu
3	S004	60	poor performance	php	manav
4	S005	55	poor performance	java	balu
...	...	...	...	...	...
114	S115	96	excellent	php	adhu
115	S116	50	poor performance	python	shone
116	S117	90	good performance	python	shan
117	S118	70	need improvement	react	Feba
118	S119	95	excellent	java	fasi

The 'feedback' and 'language' columns of the data frame are transformed into categorical variables by this block of code. Categorical variables are a sort of data that reflect categories or labels as opposed to numerical data. Fig 4 shows this.

'Poor Performance,' 'Needs Improvement,' 'Good Performance,' and 'Excellent,' in that sequence, are the categories that are applied to the 'feedback' column in this case. The categories "Python," "Java," "PHP," and "React" are listed in that order as variables for the "language" field, which has also been turned to a category variable.

```

# Convert feedback and language columns
to categorical variables
df['feedback'] = pd.Categorical(df['feed
back'], categories=['Poor Performance',
'Needs Improvement', 'Good Performance',
'Excellent'], ordered=True)

```

```
df['language'] = pd.Categorical(df['language'], categories=['Python', 'Java', 'PHP', 'React'], ordered=True)
df
```

Fig4

	STUDENT ID	avg_mark	feedback	language	name
0	S001	90	NaN	NaN	anu
1	S002	70	NaN	NaN	appu
2	S003	95	NaN	NaN	manu
3	S004	60	NaN	NaN	manav
4	S005	55	NaN	NaN	balu
...	...	...	...	...	...
114	S115	96	NaN	NaN	adhu
115	S116	50	NaN	NaN	shone
116	S117	90	NaN	NaN	shan
117	S118	70	NaN	NaN	Feba
118	S119	95	NaN	NaN	fasi

In the DataFrame df,
`# Calculate the performance metrics for each student`
`df['performance'] = pd.cut(df['avg_mark'], bins=[0, 40, 60, 80, 100], labels=['Poor', 'Average', 'Good', 'Excellent'])`
 df
 this code adds a new column called performance that, depending on each student's average grade, shows their performance level. Using the pd.cut() method, the average mark values are divided into distinct bins, and each bin is then assigned a label.

The following parameters are explicitly used to call the pd.cut() method:

The column that contains each student's mean grade is designated as df['avg_mark']. List of digits designating the bin borders: bins=[0, 40, 60, 80, 100]. In this case, there are four categories: 0-40, 40-60, 60-80, and 80-100.

label class=["Poor', 'Average', 'Good', 'Excellent']"> a list with each bin's labels listed.

As shown in Fig 5 each student's performance level is displayed in the resulting performance column based on their average score.

Fig5

	STUDENT ID	avg_mark	feedback	language	name	performance
0	S001	90	NaN	NaN	anu	Excellent
1	S002	70	NaN	NaN	appu	Good
2	S003	95	NaN	NaN	manu	Excellent
3	S004	60	NaN	NaN	manav	Average
4	S005	55	NaN	NaN	balu	Average
...	...	...	...	...	...	...
114	S115	96	NaN	NaN	adhu	Excellent

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our work has demonstrated that the Apriori algorithm may be used to pinpoint the elements that affect student performance, such as the overall grade, feedback, and language utilized. Educational authorities can utilize this data to provide targeted interventions and raise student performance. It is significant to highlight that this is only one of many potential ways for examining student performance, and further study is required to examine the efficacy of other approaches. However, our study's findings show the potential of data mining methods in the field of education.

VII. REFERENCES

[1]"Performance Analysis of Students using Apriori Algorithm" by Saini and Goyal (2020)
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